

WAYS TO EFFECTIVELY USE RESORT NATURAL AREAS IN A GREEN ECONOMY

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the possibilities of applying the concept of "green economy" for the regional development of Uzbekistan in resort natural areas. Recommendations are developed on the basis of green technologies to maintain the ecological balance of such areas, sustainable development of infrastructure and rational use of natural resources. The legal framework in this area and issues of their improvement are also described.

Keywords: resort natural areas, green economy, natural resources, environmental safety, sustainable development.

In recent years, the issue of environmental sustainability has become an urgent issue in all sectors of the economy around the world. As is known, ensuring economic growth is inextricably linked to environmental degradation and pollution, depletion of natural resources, disruption of the biosphere balance, and climate change, all of which undermine human health and limit future development opportunities. According to scientists, one of the important ways to maintain environmental sustainability, prevent climate change, and adapt to it is to "green" the economy. In particular, the development of resort natural areas is considered not only as a means of improving health, but also as a sustainable source of economic development. Sustainable development of this natural area using environmentally friendly, green innovative technologies in a market economy is one of the most important requirements of today. The UN Environment Program defines a green economy as the implementation of human well-being and social justice while reducing environmental risks and resource scarcity. The main emphasis in this regard is on:

- renewable energies;
- waste reduction;
- environmental protection.

By introducing a green economy in resort natural zones, it will be possible to combine environmental safety with economic benefits. Because resort natural areas are considered important means not only of preserving the health of the population, but also of developing regional and global tourism and providing employment, as well as economic development. According to Article 36 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protected Natural Areas", resort natural areas are protected natural areas with healing and health-improving properties, mineral springs, healing mud layers, favorable climate and other conditions. In Uzbekistan, we can name several resort natural areas, such as Zomin, Chartok, Amirsoy, Charvok, Chimyon, Aktash. These areas are rich in natural healing resources, namely mineral waters, muds, climatic conditions, which create unique opportunities for health restoration and prevention. However, their infrastructure is often outdated, and environmental safety requirements are not fully met. This increases the need for rational use and conservation of

resources. The development of resort areas based on a green economy can be carried out through alternative sources, for example, the use of renewable energy sources such as solar panels and wind, the introduction of energy-efficient heating and cooling systems, or the establishment of ecological infrastructure - clean vehicles (electric cars, bicycles), the systematic extraction of mineral waters or the introduction of water reuse technologies.

Resort natural areas can be regulated by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protected Natural Areas", "On Ecological Expertise", "On Tourism". In addition, we can say that they are closely related to regulatory documents in the field of land, water and health care. An analysis of the assessment of the modern state of the health complex in the territory of Uzbekistan shows that resort recreation should become a priority area of prospective development of tourism, as it can be a source of high income and create additional jobs in this area. Centers of medical and health tourism are sanatorium-resort institutions of various medical profiles, where a high level of service is provided, medical personnel are involved, and they serve mainly middle-aged and elderly people or people with poor health.

The issue of using resort natural areas should be considered not only in economic or environmental terms, but also within the framework of strategic planning and territorial policy. An approach based on a green economy requires not only technological innovation, but also changes in approaches to management, financing and human capital. Therefore, the involvement of local communities in the process of developing resort resources, the integration of scientific and innovative projects and the expansion of international cooperation are among the urgent tasks of today.

Also, in order to form resort areas as one of the sustainable sectors of the national economy, it is necessary to systematically assess them according to environmental, social and economic indicators, determine priorities and introduce digital management tools. This will serve as an important foundation for preserving the natural resources of Uzbekistan and achieving sustainable economic growth through them.

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